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AN ANALYSIS OF FREE TRADE AGREEMENTS BETWEEN TWO BIMSTEC NATIONS INDIA AND SRI LANKA

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Abstract

Regional collaboration is a stepping stone for economic integration in a geographic region. Economic integration might be pursuing through cooperation agreements between the nations of the region which are mostly policy induced integration. The growth of RTAs has been very rapid, particularly since 1990's. Regional economic integration between developing nations is advocate in the context of preferential and free trade arrangements, specialization, economies of scale and enlargement of markets, as most of these countries cannot attain in isolation. The India–Sri Lanka Free Trade Agreement (ISFTA) was signed between India and Sri Lanka in December 1998 and came into operation in March 2000. It is now around 15 years since this FTA has been signed and through this period the bilateral trade among these two nations has reached new heights and dimensions. This study analyzed the trade performance and term of trade between India and Sri Lanka by using the time series data from 2000 to 2013.

Keywords: Regional Trade Agreements (RTA), Exports, Imports, Term of Trade, FTA.

Introduction

In present world, no nations survive into economic isolation. Each and every aspects of economy- its industries, service sector, employment and levels of income, and living standard are associated to the economies of its trading cohorts. This association takes the shape of international arrangements of goods and services, labor, business venture, investment funds, and technology. The high level of economic interdependence between economies reflects the historical advancement of the world's economic and political regulation (Carbaugh, 2008). The recent explosion of the information technology has generated new waves of dynamism and reduced virtually the entire world into a global village. This process of increasing economic integration and growing economic interdependence among the nations of the world is widely known as globalization. By emerging in global trade, all nations can use its assets most proficiently, focused on the activities i.e. best suitable to pursue and can obtain significant economies of scale. The global trading system has been witnessing a proliferation of regional economic integration scheme or trade blocs (also known as Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs)) designed to achieve various economic and political purposes. Regional collaboration is a stepping stone for economic integration in a geographic region. It might be market determined integration with no some explicit accord implying that personal zone is energetically engaged in bringing convergence between the economies. Economic integration might also be pursuing through cooperation agreements between the nations of the region which are mostly policy induced integration. The growth of RTAs has been very rapid, particularly since 1990's. The total number of RTA up to January 2014 was 377 notified to GATT/WTO. A large additional number of RTAs are expected to become operational and substantial and 583 RTAs are proposal under negotiation (World Trade Organization, 2014). As the latest quick development of RTAs begin in 1990's but the seeds of development were arguably sown in 1980's (Cherunilam, 2006). The more frequent used forms of agreement are Preferential Trade Area, Free Trade Area, Custom Union, Common Market, Economic Union, and Economic Integration.

Regional economic integration between developing nations is advocate in the context of preferential and free trade arrangements, specialization, economies of scale and enlargement of markets, as most of these countries cannot attain in isolation. Unlike the accomplishment of economic integration among the developed nations, regional groupings in the developing world are by and great successful, barring the ASEAN which is often commended as a model of Third World regional cooperation. The SAARC, the other most important regional grouping in Asia but slow rate of progress in the SAARC was main cause for the formation of BIMSTEC in Asia. The BIMSTEC grouping, brainchild of Thailand, is a unique initiative in sub regional economic cooperation. It has the distinction of combining five geographically contiguous countries of SAARC with two of ASEAN, thus creating a vast scope for regional development. BIMSTEC is a relatively young organization among the various regional and sub regional grouping (Upreti, 2007). India and Sri Lanka are members of various regional trading blocs exist in Asia. India is member of SAARC (South Asia Association of Regional cooperation), MGC (Mekong-Ganga Cooperation), and BIMSTEC (Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation) as shown in figure. India's has trade relation with others regional trading blocs in Asia such as ASEAN (Association of Southeast Asian nations), ECO (Economic Cooperation Organization), ACD (Asia Cooperation Dialogue), GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council), and SCO (Shanghai Cooperation Organization).

BIMSTEC was initiative with the objective to merge the 'Look West' policy of Thailand and ASEAN with the 'Look East' policy of India and South Asia. The uniqueness of BIMSTEC is in multi-sectoral approach compared to other Asian blocs. On 6 June 1997, a new sub-regional alliance was created in Bangkok and given the name BIST-EC (Bangladesh, India, Sri Lanka, and Thailand Economic Cooperation). Myanmar present at the foundational June gathering as an spectator and connected the organization as a complete member at a Special Ministerial conference held in Bangkok on 22 December 1997, upon which the name of the alliance was changed to BIMSTEC. Historically, BIMSTEC came into reality very recently, its creation can be traced back to mid-1960s, when together India and Sri Lanka were invited to attach

ASEAN but declined. In 1981, Sri Lanka made vain effort to join ASEAN, but it was mutually India and Pakistan which obtained Dialogue Partner status in 1993. The approach of South Asian nations to establish connection and enlarge economic cooperation shows their purpose to support economic associations with the ASEAN countries. BIMSTEC might be used as instrument for South Asian nations to set up and enlarge a good quality relationship with the ASEAN nations (Devi, 2007).

Table No. 3: Trade Agreements Among BIMSTEC Nations.

Country's	Agreements (Bilateral and Multilateral)
India-Sri Lanka	Free Trade Agreement (FTA)
Thailand- Myanmar	ASEAN FTA
India- Thailand	FTA
SAARC nations	South Asia Preferential Trade Agreement (SAPTA)/ South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA)
India, Sri Lanka, China, Bangladesh	Bangkok Agreement
India, Nepal and Bhutan	FTA

Source: BIMSTEC.org

India's role is pivotal in the evolution and growth of BIMSTEC regional grouping. India as largest country among all member nations of BIMSTEC has the responsibility to initiate more effective and proactive measures to hasten cooperation, including by developing enduring and mutually beneficial trade, infrastructure, investment and other linkage, which alone create and sustain a vested interest in sub regional cooperation (Devi, 2007).

In the starting, the trade agreements were created between developed nations and after that the agreements among developed and developing countries on track. It is important to notice that the surge in Regional Trade Agreements is basically obsessed by highly developed economies. Conventionally the highly developed nations have always been large markets for exports from developing nations and the panorama of preferential access to such markets has induced various developing economies to search for preferential or free trade agreements among developed nations.

India- Sri Lanka Free Trade Agreement:

The India-Sri Lanka Free Trade Agreement (ISFTA) was signed among India and Sri Lanka in December, 1998 and came into process in March, 2000. After 15 years since this FTA have been signed and through FTA period the mutual trade among these two nations has reached new heights and magnitude. The FTA mainly deals with the modalities of the duty free import of the commodities manufactured within Sri Lanka. This provides chance for manufacturers from India to set up unit in Sri Lanka so that the commodities produced in Sri Lanka can able to bring into India duty free availing the exception provided in the Free Trade Arrangements. Both the nations has formed a big legal framework for collaboration i.e. free trade agreement, avoidance of double taxation agreement and a chain of mutual agreements and understanding for collaboration in the area of agriculture, small-scale industries, space, information technology, tourism, and air travel facilities.

A FTA among India and Sri Lanka has promoted equally valuable bilateral trade and strengthened intra regional economic collaboration. Underneath the accord zero duty on approximately 1000 objects has been provided by India excluding for those into the negative list. A domestic price addition requirement has been reserved at 35 per cent. With the beginning of FTA trade has developed quickly among both the nations. The FTA impelled to 257 per cent amplifies in bilateral trade between 2001 and 2004. Bilateral trades exceed US \$ 1.7 billion in 2004 and rise to US \$ 2.025 billion in 2005. India is the third biggest destination for Sri Lanka's exports. With the approval of FDI of US \$ 450 million, India is the fourth

leading investor in Sri Lanka (Chhibber, 2009). India is Sri Lanka's foremost trade associate and that mutual trade among the both nations has now reached US\$ 5 billion, it was approved that the potential which remains to enlarge mutual trade. There is a huge potential to enlarge mutual trade in a balanced manner throughout most favorable utilization of the opportunities accessible among the both nations. India emerges as Sri Lanka's foremost development partner in public investment policy also through the provision of aid and credit totaling US\$ 1.75 billion. India also assists in expanding public transport infrastructure. India's chief exports to Sri Lanka consist of automobiles, mineral fuel, pharmaceuticals, iron and steel. Imports comprise natural rubber, poultry feed, copper, paper and paper products. On the economic face, for India, Sri Lanka is a small market and account for approximately 2 per cent of Indian exports and less than 1 per cent of Indian imports. India exports to Sri Lanka varieties of goods and services as well as transport equipment, cotton yarn, fabrics, readymade garments, iron and steel, machinery and instruments, sugar and wheat, drugs and pharmaceuticals, chemicals, glass and glassware, ceramics, cement and paper and wood products and imports non-ferrous metals such as copper, spices, electronic goods, electrical machinery, scrap metal paper pulp and chemicals. India is also taken up various educational, technical training program and projects in Sri Lanka under the bilateral aid. The main objective of study is to analyze the trade performance and term of trade for India and Sri Lanka after signing the free trade agreement. Study analyze the time series data from 2000 to 2013, collected from various authentic sites such as UNCTAD (United Nation Conference on Trade and Development), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Central Bank of Sri Lanka.

Table no. 1: Indo-Sri Lankan total trade. (US\$ million)

Year	Exports of India	Imports of India	Exports of Sri Lanka	Imports of Sri Lanka	Total Indo-Sri Lankan trade
2000	59931.7	73075.2	6378.26	8105	147490.2
2001	62130.2	71311.2	6172.34	7126.39	146740.1
2002	70619.3	75741.5	5967.45	7079.34	159407.6
2003	84795	92959.1	6543.89	7683.84	191981.8
2004	116219.6	131179.9	7283.84	9107.69	263791
2005	154703.3	181978.5	7886.86	10065.57	354634.2
2006	193498.1	225268.1	8507.51	11621.22	438894.9
Average	105985.3	121644.8	6962.87	8684.15	243277.1
2007	240712.9	279416.3	9414.9	12768.55	542312.7
2008	305729	380088.5	10113	15692.02	711622.5
2009	260847.5	328257.5	8976.9	11708.4	609790.3
2010	348035	439059	11100.01	15218.56	813412.6
2011	446375	553062	13642.68	22253.82	1035334
2012	443629.47	579405.91	13573.44	21728.61	1058337
2013	464187.69	559767.39	15079.38	21508.03	1060542
Average	358502.4	445579.5	11700.04	17268.28	833050.2

Source: UNCTAD

Table no. 1 shows the Indo- Sri Lankan exports and imports flows and total trade from the period 2000 to 2013. The ISFTA (India Sri Lanka Free Trade Agreements) has contributed towards more equitable and balanced growth of bilateral trade by narrowing the trade gap between the two countries. From the period 2000 to 2006 average of total trade was US \$ 243277.1 million and from period 2006 to 2013, it increased to US \$ 833050.2 million. The average of India's export was US\$ 105985.3 million and average of India's import was US\$ 121644.8 million from the period 2000 to 2006. India's both import and export was greater as compare to Sri Lanka. During the period 2000 to 2006 averages of Sri Lanka's exports was US\$ 6962.87 million and average of imports was US\$ 8684.15 million which was less than India's export

and import. The reason behind less import export average was 70 per cent of Sri Lanka's trade has been undertaken under FTA preferences, compared to 30 per cent of India's trade. During the 2007 to 2013 the average of India's export was US\$ 358502.4 million and average of import was US\$ 445579.5 million. The average of Sri Lanka exports was US\$ 11700.28 million and average of import was US\$ 17268.28 million.

Table no. 2: Real value of India's Export and Import (Base year=2000).

Year	Unit value index of Import for India	Unit value index of export for India	*Real value of India's Imports	**Real value of India's Export
2000	100	100	73075.2	59931.7
2001	96.42	94.33	73961.89	65866.87
2002	103.65	91.86	73071.83	76876.97
2003	107.97	103.90	86100.53	81614.49
2004	135.01	116.34	97160.41	99898.82
2005	123.88	130.33	146898.3	118705.5
2006	123.84	137.19	181903.7	141048.4
Average			104596	91991.82
2007	138.33	157.93	201992.5	152416.7
2008	149.63	175.42	254022.4	174284.9
2009	120.98	159.29	271339.2	163759
2010	144.74	191.85	303333.7	181410.7
2011	175.00	223.31	316042.4	199888.1
2012	174.47	222.87	332092.6	199056.7
2013	166.27	217.96	336659.6	212966.5
Average			287926.1	183397.5

Source: UNCTAD

*Real import is calculated by (Import/unit value index base year 2000)*100.

**Real export is calculated by (Export/unit value index base year 2000)*100.

Table no. 2 depicts the real value of exports and import of India from the period 2000 to 2013 base year 2000. The average of India imports from 2000 to 2006 was US \$ 104596 million and from the period 2007 to 2013 averages of India's import was US \$ 287926.1 million. There was three times increment was noticed in real value of imports. The average of India exports from 2000 to 2006 was US \$ 91991.82 million and from the period 2007 to 2013 averages of India's export was US \$ 183397.5 million. There was two times increment was noticed in real value of exports. An export from India was less as compared to India's import.

Table no. 3: Real value of Sri Lankan Export and Import (Base year=2000).

Year	Unit value index of Import for Sri Lanka	unit value index of export for Sri Lanka	Real value of Sri Lanka's Imports	Real value of Sri Lanka's Export
2000	100.00	100	8105	6378.26
2001	98.54	95.37	7231.868	6472.133
2002	102.08	93.44	6934.921	6386.672
2003	103.07	95.73	7454.863	6836.117
2004	111.36	99.46	8178.932	7323.514
2005	113.67	102.20	8855.47	7716.902
2006	121.37	107.32	9574.74	7927.541
Average			8047.97	7005.87

2007	122.20	110.05	10448.63	8555.219
2008	127.24	119.45	12333.03	8466.004
2009	102.86	121.93	11382.71	7362.13
2010	124.80	127.45	12194.44	8709.1
2011	158.87	142.55	14007.74	9570.757
2012	152.76	144.55	14224	9390.049
2013	145.00	135.99	14833.36	11088.4
Average			12774.84	9020.23

Source: UNCTAD

*Real import is calculated by (Import/unit value index base year 2000)*100.

**Real export is calculated by (Export/unit value index base year 2000)*100

Table no. 3 depicts the real value of exports and import of Sri Lanka from the period 2000 to 2013 base year 2000. The average of Sri Lanka imports from 2000 to 2006 was US \$ 8047.97 million and from the period 2007 to 2013 averages of Sri Lanka's import was US \$ 12774.84 million. The average of Sri Lanka exports was increased US\$ 7005.87 million (2000 to 2006) to US\$ 9020.23 million during the period 2007 to 2013. An export from Sri Lanka was less as compared to its import. The number of products exported by Sri Lanka to India increased substantially during the time of 2000 to 2013.

Table no.4: Term of trade for Indo Sri Lankan trade (in Per cent).

Year	India			Sri Lanka		
	Net Barter Term of Trade	Gross Barter Term of Trade	Income Term of Trade	Net Barter Term of Trade	Gross Barter Term of Trade	Income Term of Trade
2000	100	100	100	100	100	100
2001	97.83	93.52	106.12	96.78	105.96	90.00
2002	88.62	83.65	112.12	91.53	110.22	84.77
2003	96.23	97.40	128.87	92.87	104.54	91.57
2004	86.17	92.26	133.96	89.32	104.47	95.21
2005	105.20	124.11	189.75	89.92	99.39	102.83
2006	110.78	133.46	232.09	88.42	102.72	104.47
Average	97.83	103.49	143.27	92.69	103.9	95.5
2007	114.17	143.45	256.14	90.05	94.35	116.64
2008	117.24	158.90	307.25	93.88	97.65	122.33
2009	131.67	168.91	321.65	118.54	92.72	131.50
2010	132.54	168.69	369.00	102.13	100.41	126.93
2011	127.61	160.95	408.44	89.73	120.14	118.65
2012	127.74	172.96	401.42	94.63	127.83	113.08
2013	131.09	160.80	443.35	93.79	108.16	125.74
Average	126.01	162.09	358.18	97.54	105.89	122.12

Table no. 4 depicts the term of trade among India and Sri Lanka. During the period from 2000 to 2006 India's Net Barter Term of Trade (NBTOT) was higher than Sri Lanka as shown in table. The average of India NBTOT was 97.83 per cent where as average of Sri Lanka's NBTOT was 92.69 per cent. But during the period 2007 to 2013 average of India's NBTOT was increased as compared to Sri Lanka's NBTOT, it was 126.01 per cent. The Gross Barter Term of Trade (GBTOT) was almost same for both the countries

during the period of 2000 to 2006, it was 103.49 per cent for India and 103.9 per cent for Sri Lanka. But from 2007 to 2013, the average of GBTOT was India's increased at much higher rate as compared to Sri Lanka. India's GBTOT was 162.09 per cent during 2007 to 2013 and average off Sri Lanka's GBTOT was 105.89 per cent. In case of Sri Lanka only 2 per cent increment in GBTOT was noticed. India was also lead in Income Term of Trade (ITOT) as compared to Sri Lanka. During the 2000 to 2006 the average of ITOT of India's was 143.27 per cent and it increased to 358.18 per cent in 2007 to 2013. The average of Sri Lanka's ITOT was 95.5 during 2000 to 2006 and it increased to 122.12 per cent in 2007 to 2013. India was more efficient in term of trade as compared to Sri Lanka. So from above analysis, concluded that term of trade was favourable for India as compare to Sri Lanka. In all types of term of trade India gains for than Sri Lanka. For the initial years of the free trade agreement among both the nations (2000 to 2006), it was noticed that the growth of trade was not much higher but after that period trade among both the nations increased rapidly.

Table no.5: Trends and Forecast of trade among India and Sri Lanka.

Year	Total Indo- Sri Lankan trade	Trends and forecasting of trade
2000	147490	133618
2001	146740	159588
2002	159408	190608
2003	191982	227656
2004	263791	271905
2005	354634	324755
2006	438895	387878
2007	542313	463270
2008	711623	553316
2009	609791	660863
2010	813413	789315
2011	1035334	942734
2012	1058337	1125973
2013	1060542	1344829
2014		1606223
2015		1918424
2016		2291308
2017		2736669
2018		3268595
2019		3903912
2020		4662715
2021		5569006
2022		6651452
2023		7944294

Table no. 6.2 depicts the trends and forecast of India and Sri Lanka total trade. The trade among two countries increased because both countries remove the tariff and also exempt the duties on imported and exported goods. From above projections, it is concluded that, trade among both the nations, will be beneficial in future.

Figure no.1: Trends and Forecast of trade among India and Sri Lanka.

Projections had been made for the total trade among India and Sri Lanka at current prices on the basis of their actual performance during 2000 to 2013. Both can trade US\$ 7944294 million in 2025. Thus, based on Indi Sri Lankan actual trade, there exists a scope for her trade in future. Therefore, more efforts are required to be made to increase the trade and earn a fair name in the world trade.

Conclusion:

No doubt, the Free Trade Agreement (FTA) among both the nations is important step ahead but lots of requirements to be done in close future to construct a actual achievement story. In current years the India and Sri Lanka economic relations has turn into a kind of model collaboration into the South Asian region. But there is scope for development. At present there are a huge amount of items in the negative lists as well as quantitative restrictions on trade which can be restricting the trade among both nations. Already both the countries have concluded negotiations for the next pace of economic integration by expediting the Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA). On the other hand, there are several sensible difficulties which require to be sorted out. Tea and textiles are the main exports in both the nations. Therefore, both the nations frequently struggle in the similar market. But the worldwide economic recession calls for more collaboration to offset the impact. Sri Lanka's exports to India have surged under a FTA, rising six fold, with the number of objects departing up four fold but the majority of the imports to the island take place outside the agreement. On average 70 percent of Sri Lanka's exports to India are under the free trade agreement, compared to only 30 percent Indian exports coming to Sri Lanka under the FTA. Sri Lanka's exports to India have improved from 1 percent on the whole export before the FTA to almost 6 percent. At last, for both nations FTA created a positive trade environment.

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